

The Episcopal Church of Cherubim and Seraphim, Zion Pepe

By Adegbola Tolu Adefi, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Aladura, The Episcopal Church of Cherubim and Seraphim, Zion Pepe

The Episcopal Church of Cherubim and Seraphim, Zion Pepe was established on January 2, 1951 by a group predominantly made up of Ilaje men and women who lived or hailed from the Etikan and Aheri axis of Ilajeland. They had previously subscribed to the Cherubim and Seraphim Society which made its way into Ilajeland in 1929 and had continued to pursue their spiritual enlightenment with the Cherubim and Seraphim Church, Ugbonla from February 16, 1948 when that movement became distinct from the erstwhile Cherubim and Seraphim movement in Ilajeland. Worshippers at Ugbonla who travelled from Aheri and Etikan area of Ilajeland often had tortuous journeys to the community, They had to travel in dugout canoes for hours and at times in the rain. Apostle Theophilus Erejuwa Mafo, an associate of Saint Elisha Lene Ogunfeyimi then took it upon himself to establish another Zion community in the fringes of Etikan and Aheri. He moved to an uninhabited land (Zion Pepe) off his natal settlement of Ipepe to begin a new Zion which began to serve the spiritual enlightenment desire of C & S members in that area of Ilajeland. The church founded by Saint Mafo took up a hybrid name collapsing the nomenclature of the Episcopal church in his natal settlement with the C & S movement he was introducing there. Thus he tagged the church the Episcopal Church of Cherubim and Seraphim, Zion Pepe. The structure, operational guidelines, doctrines, beliefs and practices of the church are like those held by the C & S Zion, Ugbonla. However, the clerical order and titles of religious specialists in the community differ from those used in Ugbonla. As a theocratic settlement, the community holds religious meetings twice daily in the only religious house built and permitted within its borders. The religious specialists in the community daily bring the congregation inspiring sermons, songs in the spiritually charged atmosphere. The community's annual conventions and anniversaries are moments of spiritual rejuvenation and revival. Compared to other theocratic communities in Ilajeland, Zion Pepe seems to have enjoyed more stable succession processes to the throne. Of the six Obas (monarchs) who have reigned in the community, only once was there some dispute in the process leading to the selection of the successor. The community also appears to be liberal when scouting for the a new Oba. They have brought prophets who were domiciled in branches of the church to lead the community while passing over some other powerful and eligible prophets in the headquarters. Zion Pepe continues to enjoy a stable spiritual atmosphere as it has also made considerable gains in their social and economic aspirations.

Date Range: 1951 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Southwest, Nigeria

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Nigeria

Zion Pepe community in Ilaje Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria. It is the headquarters of the Episcopal Church of Cherubim and Seraphim worldwide, Zion Pepe. The community was founded on January, 2, 1951

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Omoyajowo, J. Akinyele, *Cherubim and Seraphim: The History of an African Independent Church* (New York: NOK, 1982)
- Source 2: Omogbemi, C.O, *Leneism: Key to Zion Renaissance* (Lagos: Inspiration Communications, 2008)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

- Source 1: *Religious Expressions, Theocratic Communities and Cultural Identity in the Ilaje Coastline of Southwest Nigeria since 1930.*

Notes: No extensive work has been done on the Episcopal Cherubim and Seraphim Church, Zion Pepe. Only passing references have been made to the Zion brand of the C & S church in works on the Aladura Movement in Nigeria. In some cases, these references are as brief as few sentences or just a paragraph in the few books available. The source referenced above is the PhD thesis of this author which focussed on four of the most prominent theocratic settlements in Ilajeland. Zion Pepe is one of the four theocratic settlements studied in the work. The thesis was written in the department of Religious Studies and submitted to the Postgraduate College of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. It was completed in late 2020

Specific to this answer:

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Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.africanportal.net/ABO/BibeliAtoka/>
- Source 1 Description: Yoruba bible (Atoka)

Specific to this answer:

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is the cultural contact competitive:

- No

Notes: Zion Pepe theocratic community relates with other theocratic villages in Ilajeland. However, their relationship is not that of competition. There are about fifty theocratic

communities in Ilajeland. Each of them operates within its territory. There is no proselyting of the members of a group by the other. When one of the theocratic communities has a convention, an anniversary or any special programme, they extend invitations to theocratic communities around them to participate in their programme and share their joy at such momentous occasions.

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↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact which Zion Pepe has with her neighbours (other theocratic communities in Ilajeland) is accommodating to the extent that they all get along well by exchanging invitation with one another for special programmes, anniversaries and conventions.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact Zion Pepe has with her neighbours is not just neutral. It is more of positive and accommodating

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: There are no violent conflicts within the sample region of Zion Pepe

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↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: No records exists regarding violent conflicts with groups outside the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Though birth in Zion Pepe or to parents who belong to Zion Pepe theocratic community confirms limited membership rights on the children, the full membership right is not attained until members (usually adults) attend and graduate from the community's theology school which hold biennially.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership of the Zion Pepe theocratic community is by personal choice. No one is compelled to join the community against their wish.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Class is not a determining factor neither does it constitute a ground towards assigning membership of Zion Pepe community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Age is not a consideration towards assigning membership of Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: There is no restriction on membership of Zion Pepe community on account of gender. Both males and females are allowed to exercise their rights to join the community.

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Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Full membership of Zion Pepe community is assigned after intending members successfully attend the community's theology school which holds for six months (from July to December) biennially.

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Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Full membership of Zion Pepe is assigned after intending members successfully attend the community's theology school which holds for six months (from July to December) biennially.

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Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The nature of the growth and expansion of Zion Pepe community is such that it thrives on its interventions in crisis situations which people find themselves. When the community was founded, it was reported to have made numerous interventions in the personal lives of people who eventually became her members. Sicknesses and other life crisis which had held people down were reported to have been miraculously cured or removed. These interventions attracted more members and led to membership explosion in Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Though the Zion Pepe community does not have official political support, it has participated actively in the political process in its region. In fact, the son of the founder of the community was the first political head of the Local Government (authority) in the area.

Specific to this answer:

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Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Members of the Zion Pepe community are quite resolute in their belief. The issue of apostasy has not been recorded in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000

Notes: Zion Pepe as the headquarters of the Episcopal C & S Church of Zion worldwide has a population of permanent residents in excess of 1000 adults. However, when members of the church living outside of this town and who worship regularly in church branches in their various locations are reckoned, the number would rise significantly to more than 30000. Nigeria's national population census conducted in 1991 puts the figure of Zion Pepe's population at 1,225. The population grew significantly over the years owing to Zion Pepe's influence in its environment. However, the number of permanent adult residents in the town gradually declined to its current size of about 1000. This is due primarily to the rural-urban population drift in Nigeria. Several hundreds others have become less active and so may not be regarded as active members anymore.

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2.44

Notes: This estimate is based on the figures of Nigeria's 1991 population census. The Ilaje Local Government under which Zion Pepe falls was reported to have a population size of 50,188 while Zion Pepe had a total of 1225 residents. The national census conducted in 2006 was not very successful and that which was planned for 2022 was postponed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Zion Pepe is an autonomous religious group in Ilaje Local Government Area of Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria. It is one of the four most prominent of the nearly fifty theocratic communities in the Ilaje area. It has several branches within and outside Ilajeland. The major activities of the branches are controlled from Zikon Pepe, the headquarters of the religious community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The Oba (king/monarch) is the spiritual and political head of the community. He is supported by prophets and elders who assist him in administering the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe leaders are generally conceived as possessing powers which are not common with most people. They are seen as being capable of making spiritual interventions in the lives of their followers such that problems and difficulties which have defied natural solutions become resolved by spiritual means. They cure sicknesses, barrenness, poverty and other problems by spiritual means. These interventions resulted in the population explosion the community witnessed during the lifetime of the founder. However, the people admit that the powers possessed by the Oba and the prophets are derived from the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not believe in the idea of a past life neither do they hold that the quality of life lived in a purported past life has an impact or influence on the powers exhibited by anyone in the current life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that, to a certain extent, the quality of self-sacrifice made by individuals determines the level of spiritual impact they would have. Their prophets spend quality time seeking the high god. They study the scriptures, pray and invest time in personal devotion to the high god. This, according to them, accounts for their spiritual capacity. They however hold that ultimately, the decision to reveal himself to anyone lies with the high god.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not believe powers are transferable from parents to children. The community has a unique succession plan. None of the five or six previous Obas of the community has had their children become Obas either succeeding them or reigning at some time in the history of the community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe community when an Oba is translated from this realm of existence the church leaders and elders pray and are guided through the process of selecting a new Oba. They rely on the guidance of the holy Spirit as they make the choice of the new leader.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: No human being culturally transmits powers to a new leader in Zion Pepe community. The community leaders prays and select a new Oba who becomes the spiritual and political head of community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: The leadership office an individual occupies determines the powers they wield and the influence they exercise in Zion Pepe theocratic community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: The prophets and leaders in Zion Pepe community decide on who becomes the next Oba after the demise of an Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: Recognised leaders in Zion Pepe community decide on who becomes the next Oba. Though they would have worked with the departed Oba, they are not strictly regarded as his ministers but as ministers of the community. They therefore decide on the choice of the next Oba as a matter of responsibility in the overall interest of the community and not as loyalists of the departed Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

Notes: The duty of choosing a new Oba for Zion Pepe community is the responsibility of the recognised leaders of the community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: The Zion Pepe community is autonomous of the influence of political leaders. No political leader has a role to play towards the emergence of the Oba of Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: The responsibility of selecting a new Oba in Zion Pepe is that of the prophets and elders/community leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: The responsibility of selecting a new Oba in Zion Pepe is that of the prophets and elders/community leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: The prophets and leaders of the community communicate with the high god or his spirit (the Holy Spirit) in selecting a new Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders in Zion Pepe are not considered as completely perfect to the extent that they cannot make mistakes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Though the community does not consider their leaders as infallible, the members have enormous respect for their leaders that they do not frivolously bring charges of fallibility against them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Leaders at other leaders in Zion Pepe community do not consider their leaders as infallible. However, they have enormous respect for their Oba that they do not frivolously bring charges of fallibility against them.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community has never found itself in a situation where a political ruler has had to bring charges of fallibility against its Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and

unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Close followers or disciples of Zion Pepe's religious leader obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters. However, there are a few occasions when they find acceptable avenue to make the leader see the issues from their own perspective. They do not however insist that the Oba must change his decision in favour of their views.

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group beliefs in the authority of the Holy Bible

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: The scriptures used in Zion Pepe are not oral

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community holds that the high god is the originator of the scriptures. In originating it however, he used other supernatural beings including the angels as vehicles of transmitting the scriptures to the prophets who received inspiration to write the revelations or dealings they got from the supernatural realm.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The other supernatural beings like the angels who featured in the canonised scriptures were only agents of the supreme being. They had no authority outside that which the supreme being gave them.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community hold that all scripture is given (inspired) by the high god. This is what the scripture say of itself

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↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: No other supernatural being apart from the high god inspired the writing of the scriptures

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: There is no allusion to the bible as having originated from divine or semi-divine human beings

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↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that the bible originated from non-divine human beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community church, the church secretariat and the mausoleums of all former Obas of the community make up the bulk of the religious monuments in the community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 2

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1000

Notes: The church is the largest religious monument in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

Notes: The church tower is the highest religious monument in Zion Pepe

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 500

Notes: The church secretariat is an average monument in Zion Pepe community

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 18

Notes: The church secretariat has an height of 18 meters

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 5

Notes: This figure covers the area taken up by the church, the church secretariat, the mausoleums and the community cemetery.

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Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: This includes the tombs/mausoleums of all the past kings and the first Choirmaster General of the community.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: The community cemetery is a large one. It was set up in the 1980s when the community decided to create a separate space for burying their departed ones

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↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The community church is the biggest and most important religious monument in Zion Pepe

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: The monarch of Zion Pepe sits at the altar at every church meeting

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↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of devotional markers in Zion Pepe. They are mostly physical objects with spiritual significance. Some of them include swords, crosses, flags, pictures of angels etc

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↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The church is the most significant gathering point for religious activities in Zion Pepe community. Some meetings also hold at the church secretariat or the palace of the reigning Oba

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↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Every Oba who reigns in Zion Pepe builds himself a house which serves as their palace. these houses are usually built to taste. All past Obas of the community have all built for themselves one-storey building all on different streets within the community.

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Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: The usage of iconography is quite common in Zion Pepe community. Members of the community hoist flags around their houses to signify two purposes. When the red flag is used, it signifies warfare. When the community speaks of spiritual battles, they entertain no other thoughts but that of victory. When white flags are hoisted outside their homes, this signifies peace. By hoisting the white flags, they are calling for calm and peace to their troubling situations. Some of the prayer garments in use in Zion Pepe also have their unique significance. When the Cherubim band or anyone uses a red prayer garment, they are again speaking of warfare. This may be used during the Holy Michael Festival which the Cherubim Band spearheads or at any other period when an individual sees the need to fight a personal spiritual warfare.

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↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

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↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Notes: Pictures of the eyes are not included in Zion Pepe's iconography

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↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, there is the notion of the high god hiding his saints under the shadow of his wings. This infers that the supreme being is conceived of as having the qualities of birds, a member of the animal kingdom.

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↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

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↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community speak of the high god as having human qualities. They often describe him as having an everlasting arm, as having eyes which run through the whole earth or as a God who makes the heaven his home and the earth his footstool.

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↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community are clear in their minds about the nature of the supreme being though they are prohibited from having any physical representation of him.

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↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The people of Zion Pepe community have an idea of the beauty of heaven. They describe heaven as having streets of gold, peaceful rivers and immeasurable delight. They have a clear idea and a vivid imagination of how the blissful afterlife will be.

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The community uses wooden swords and cross to symbolise some of the aspects of their faith. The swords are deployed in symbolic warfare which they are expected to win at all times. This is because they represent the light. It is a common belief among them that darkness can never overcome the light. On the other hand, the cross symbolises the suffering of Christ. They see it as the wisdom of the supreme being in bringing victory to humankind through the way of the cross (suffering)

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↳ Humans:

– No

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↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community also conceive of their spiritual enemy (the devil or satan) as an ugly personality. When talking about the enemy of their souls they use an ugly and cruel personality to represent him.

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Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: There is a site in front of the Zion Pepe community church building dedicated to the conduct of spiritual investigation by the Cherubim band. The site is called "So otito" (speak the truth) in the local language. When an investigation into a civil or criminal matter is ongoing and it proves difficult to unravel, suspects are advised to be truthful under oath. They are then taken to the spot believed to have been energised by some spiritual means. Anyone who gets to the spot and yet tells lies would be struck by some strange powers which would overwhelm the fellow and make them sick until they confess. No one goes to the site and insists on peddling falsehood.

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Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: There is a pool of water around the community pier which is reported to be potent to bring healing to people suffering from various forms of sicknesses and those being tormented by strange spirits. Scores of individuals have reportedly received healing and restoration from their distressing conditions after their encounter with the pool of water.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Every member of the Zion Pepe church in the diaspora is encouraged to attend special programmes in the community as a mark of their commitment to the church. Opportunities abound during their anniversaries, conventions and convocations to make such visits.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: Full members (those who have undergone the church theology training) are expected to attend the General Assembly of the ordained workers yearly.

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Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The belief in Zion Pepe community is that the body and spirit-mind are distinct components of the human essence. Without the spirit, the body cannot perform the basic functions it is known to perform. Likewise, without the body, the spirit is incapacitated to express itself.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-mind is seen in Zion Pepe as having qualitatively different powers or properties than the other body parts. The spirit is conceived of as being the human essence. It outlives the body such that after the death and decay of the human body, the spirit still lives to either enjoy the good deeds it did while in the body or be subjected to eternal anguish if it lived in disregard to the instructions of the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, the spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material and clearly distinct from the physical body.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Notes: There are no other clearly defined spirit-body relationship in the belief system of Zion

Pepe community. However, some of Zion Pepe population are partially (unofficially) influenced by some of the cultural beliefs in natal communities around them. One of such beliefs held in communities around them is that a human spirit could depart a body but instead of going to rest in paradise as held in Zion Pepe, such spirit could look for another body to inhabit in order to carry out some deeds considered important which it was unable to accomplish before death. This is usually ascribed to those who die prematurely. Natal villages in Ilajeland hold this belief to be true for those, who, especially die young.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community beliefs that there is an afterlife at the end of this current life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The spatial location of the afterlife is specified in the theology of Zion Pepe

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe belief system, there are two distinct locations where the afterlife would be lived or spent. The good folks would spend their afterlife in the skyey heavens in resplendent bliss while evil people will have be held in Hades or hell. This is a place of torment and anguish.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: The afterlife in Zion Pepe theology is clearly defined in terms of space and experience.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, the afterlife in Hades or hell is clearly defined as a space below.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: The location of the afterlife in Zion pepe theology is well defined. It is not in an horizontal space in relation to the earth's location.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not part of Zion Pepe theology. The community beliefs that it is appointed unto humans to die once and after this comes judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There are no special treatments for adherents' corpses in Zion Pepe. The corpses are prepared in the normal way their kith and kin in Yorubaland prepare the corpses of their departed for burial and are interred in similar ways without any "special" treatment for the corpses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not practice co-sacrifices as part of their burial rites.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe does not believe in nor practice the custom of presenting grave goods to their dead during burial rites.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are conducted in Zion Pepe community for their departed members who lived in the headquarters of the church. Other members who lived in other communities outside the headquarters are buried in the communities where they lived during their lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: Zion community does not engage in wars or military campaigns are part of their religious or devotional obligations. Therefore, their members have not been casualties of religious wars for which cenotaphs would be conducted or erected in their honour.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe is the only theocratic community among the four religious communities in Ilajeland which has a dedicated cemetery for burying their dead.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: There are no family tomb-crypts in Zion Pepe. All their departed members except the Obas or other very important functionaries are buried in the community cemetery. The Obas and important functionaries are buried in mausoleums beside the church building.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic

activities):

– No

Notes: Usually, Zion Pepe community buries their departed members in the community tomb. None of their members is interred beneath houses or in other areas used for normal domestic activities. Apart from the cemetery, the only place where a few qualified members (Oba and important functionaries) get interred is in mausoleums beside the church

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no other burial types known in Zion Pepe except burials in the community cemetery or the ones in mausoleums beside the community church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community has a well developed theology around an all powerful, all knowing and benevolent supernatural being

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god in Zion Pepe theology is often described anthropomorphically. He is said to possess hands, eyes, feet and other body parts akin to those of human beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe belief their supreme high god is a sky deity

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community beliefs their supreme high god lives in the skyey heaven and that he is not a god of the underworld.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not belief their supreme high god is fused with their monarch. He is distinct and much higher in rank compared to their monarch.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community belief their monarch is a manifestation or emanation of the supreme high god just the same way everyone of them is an emanation of the same god. The only distinction they hold with regard to this is that their monarch is chosen by the high god to lead them and show them the way of the high god

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community has a clear distinction between the status of the high god and that of their elites. Their belief is that the supreme high god is no march with the elites. The elites are his creation and therefore subject to him

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: There is no loyalty-connection between the supreme high god and the elites in

Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the supreme high god is unquestionably good. They conceive of him as having no capacity to do evil. They do not subscribe to the theory of theodicy which suggests that it is either that the supreme high god is all good but not all powerful. The theory of theodicy questions the supposed unquestionably good high god who cannot stop prevent evil from happening to good people. The explanation the community gives to counter the proponents of the theory of theodicy is that the supreme high god has given all men a free will to decide how to conduct themselves. He would however require of every being how the exercised their discretion regarding their free will. He will either use the law of karma to reward every action or wait till the last day to bring every action to judgement. Their theology is centred around the unquestionably good god who is not overtly imposing on the free will he has given to every being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god is conceived of as being unquestionably benevolent, loving, kind and as being a god of justice. He is also held among the Zion Pepe community as being caring, being a provider and as a god of vengeance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe holds that the supreme god's knowledge is not restricted to any particular domain of human affairs. He is conceived of as an all knowing god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not hold that the high god's knowledge is restricted to a specific area within the sample region. His knowledge is never restricted to any single or particular location. He knows what is happening in every place in the universe all at the same time. He does not do a catch-up of events in anyway.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region. According to them, his knowledge is universal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community holds that the supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region. He knows what is going on everywhere at every moment. He is also conceived as the custodian of all past and future events and hidden secrets which are not known by any other mortal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe believes that the supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public) at all times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community hold that the supreme high god can see each

individual everywhere irrespective of whether they are in the dark while at home or not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, there is the belief that the supreme high god can see inside the heart/mind and can also see every hidden hidden motive of every human being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, there is the belief that the supreme high god knows the basic character (personal essence) of every being. They hold that absolutely nothing is hidden from him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe theocratic community believes that the supreme high god knows what will happen to every mortal and what they will do in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Zion Pepe theocratic community holds that all knowledge/secret is known by the supreme high god. In the community, the supreme high god is held as being aware of every bit of known and unknown facts. This includes facts regarding past, present and future events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the supreme high god has deliberate causal

efficacy in the world. In this community, the supreme high god is held as being the originator of all that there is in the whole world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the supreme high god is the most suited or qualified being to reward all actions because he sees all hidden things which are not visible to other mortals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe holds that the supreme high god can punish. They agree that he is the most perfect being suited for visiting punishments on wrongdoers. This is because they hold that his eyes are everywhere and at every time. He sees what everyone does in the open or in the dark. With this ability, he cannot punish the innocent and allow the wrongdoer go free.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, the supreme high god has direct causal efficacy as opposed to an indirect causal efficacy in the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community the supreme high god is seen as possessing positive emotions like kindness, joy, love etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not consider the supreme high god as one who displays negative emotions needlessly. In fact of the numerous negative emotions that there are, Zion Pepe does not associate the supreme high god with any except anger. His anger in their theology is towards the evil doers who according to them deserve such treatment having used their free will to do wrong. The supreme high god is therefore under the obligation to directly punish them or deploy the law of karma to mete out the treatment they deserve.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god in the estimation of Zion Pepe community does not hunger for food. He is described by them as one who after much patience with evil doers may grow in his anger and hunger for visiting them with the rewards of their evil actions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community is intolerant of the worship of any other supernatural being(s) apart from the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Zion Pepe community holds that the supreme high god possesses or exhibits some other feature which include mercy, forgiveness to repentant folks and vengeance to unrepentant folks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community believes that the supreme high god communicates with the living in waking, everyday life. However, everyone who must enjoy conversations with him must him/herself be committed to him irrevocably. In this community, the prophets are acknowledged to have greater access and conversations with the supreme being. This is because they hear him always and devote relatively greater amounts of time to seek him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community talk about how that the supreme high god communicates with them in dreams. In fact during their daily early morning church meetings, sometime is devoted to allow those who have had some encounter in their dreams to tell the congregation what they had encountered in their dreams or trances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community talk about how that the supreme high god communicates with them in dreams. In fact during their daily early morning church meetings, sometime is devoted to allow those who have had some encounter to tell the congregation what they had encountered in their dreams or trances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The divination practice in Zion Pepe is their congregational, group or individual prayer times. The people are ever eager to tell how their high god speaks to them during such spiritual exercises.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The people of Zion Pepe often tell of how the supreme high god speaks to them as individuals. Though the people are in agreement on how the religious specialists like the prophets enjoy some form of closer interactions

with the high god, this does not foreclose the fact that the high god equally speaks to others apart from the religious specialists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The people are in agreement on how the monarch who is usually a prophet enjoys closer interactions with the high god, this does not foreclose the fact that the high god equally speaks to others apart from the monarch.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Zion Pepe community tell of how the supreme high god speaks to them through the scriptures and through circumstances which they find themselves in daily

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of human spirits which once trod the earth or more strictly the Ilaje landscape is not usually felt physically. However, the spiritually inclined (prophets) do have encounters with them occasionally. For the general human population of Zion Pepe, feeling their presence is the exception rather than the rule

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: It is held that spirits of the living and the dead are ubiquitous in Ilajeland. Zion Pepe believes in the existence of the spirits of the departed but they do not think of the spirits as being visible to the human eyes. The spirits of the living are however the essence of humankind. Without the spirit, humans will simply become corpses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of human spirits which ones trod the earth or more strictly the Ilaje landscape is not usually felt physically. However, the spiritually inclined (prophets) do have encounters with them occasionally. However, for the generality of the human population of Zion Pepe, feeling their presence is the exception rather than the rule. In Zion Pepe, as the believe goes, the spirits of the living cannot be felt.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that spirits of those who previously walked the universe have considerable knowledge of the world. These spirits are however generally conceived to operate within the region where they trod in their previous lives. They are conceived of continuing with tasks they were prevented from completing due to untimely death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, it seems very convincing that human spirits are generally restricted to particular domain of human affairs. However, when under the influence of the divine spirit, human spirits gain access to the realm beyond their usual scope. of operation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Except they are empowered by supernatural means, Zion Pepe holds that human spirits knowledge is restricted to specific areas within the sample region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Except they are empowered by supernatural means, Zion Pepe holds that human spirits knowledge is restricted to specific areas within the sample region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe, human spirits are held as having little or no knowledge outside the sample region except when such spirits have had personal experience in specific regions outside their homeland.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, human spirits of living beings are incapable of seeing other beings everywhere normally visible (in public). However, spirits of the departed have the ability to see humans everywhere normally visible (in public). This is because they have transcended the physical limitations imposed by their entrapment in the human body.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, human spirits of living beings are incapable of seeing other beings everywhere normally visible (in the dark, at home). However, spirits of the departed have the ability to see humans everywhere normally visible (in the dark, at home). This is because they have transcended the physical limitations imposed by their entrapment in the human body.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, human spirits of living beings are incapable of seeing the inside of the heart or mind (hidden motives). However, spirits of the departed have the ability to see inside the heart/mind (hidden motives). This is because they have transcended the physical limitations imposed by their entrapment in the human body and have taken up some of the attributes of the supernatural world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, human spirits of living beings are incapable of knowing the basic character of others. However, spirits of the departed have the ability to know these characters. This is because they have transcended the physical limitations imposed by their entrapment in the human body and have attained some attributes of supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, human spirits of living beings are incapable of knowing what will happen to others or what others will do in future. However, spirits of the departed have the ability to know what will happen to others or what they will do in the future. This is because they have transcended the physical limitations imposed by their entrapment in the human body and have taken up some attributes of the supernatural beings..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

Notes: No other forms of knowledge apart from those obtained through learning and empirical means are available to human spirits regarding the world. However, spirits of the dead are assumed to possess other forms of knowledge obtained through their transcendence of the limitations of this world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The belief in Zion Pepe regarding human spirits is that they do not in themselves possess deliberate causal efficacy. Zion Pepe theology perceives human spirits as emanating from the supreme high god. The community holds that human spirits have been given the free will to follow a path or a line of action independently. However, their choice will necessarily attract an appropriate reward or punishment in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The belief in Zion Pepe regarding human spirits is that they do not in themselves possess deliberate causal efficacy. Zion Pepe theology perceives human spirits as emanating from the supreme high god. The community holds that human spirits have been given the free will to follow a path or a line of action independently. However, their choice will necessarily attract an appropriate reward or punishment in the afterlife. The community holds that once the human spirit engages in a line of action, such action generates a consequence. This consequence may lead to another action and a further action ad infinitum. This leads to a series of consequences. However, the community equally believes that the human spirit has capacity to change the nature of their behaviours which would necessarily affect the nature of their subsequent rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that human spirits have memory of life. This believe can be explained by how the human being is able to reward past favours from a friend with a good turn or how they pay back a wrong done them by another with an action commensurate with how they were treated by the same fellow.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that it is the human spirit that strengthens the resolve of all individuals on any chosen course of action. The human spirit is believed to exhibit positive emotions which include expression of love, compassion, forgiveness, bravery, sympathy, faith, hope etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community holds that the human spirit exhibits negative emotions which include expression of anger, regret, vengeance, disloyalty, hatred, greed, selfishness etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

Notes: In most cases, Zion Pepe community does not project human spirits as having the capacity for hunger. They sometimes conceive of them as having the power to be hungry for revenge or reward for actions done to them or their loved ones in the past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Although they do not have official roles to play in the community, they unofficially form a part of the human ecosystem in Zion Pepe. They are given credit for a range of happenings in the lives of individuals and families they belong to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that human spirits communicate with the living in waking, everyday life. The community holds that spirits of the departed (at their pleasure) interact with the living by giving them instructions or passing other vital information to them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community believes the spirits of the departed interact with the living in dreams. Several of them confirm that their departed parents have one time or the other appeared to them in their dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community believes the spirits of the departed interact with

the living in their trances. Several of them confirm that their departed relations have one time or the other appeared to them in trances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not interact with human spirits through divination. Therefore spirits do not interact with them through divination processes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: Specialists do not interface between the community of the living and the departed in Zion Pepe. Therefore, human spirits are not contacted through specialists in Zion Pepe. Strictly speaking, Zion Pepe does not have a cult of the ancestors or have an obligation towards their departed ones. However, they only acknowledge their informal interactions with living members of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The monarch does not hold an official position in the dynamics of relations between the living and the spirits of the departed in Zion Pepe. As a matter of fact, there are no official protocols in the relationships that exist between members of the community and the spirits of the departed. Individuals only speak of private interactions with the spirits of their departed relations in their dreams, trances etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: In an informal manner, individuals in Zion Pepe speak of the spirits of their revered relations returning into the family as new born babies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community recognises the presence and participation of angels in their private and collective affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Angels as supernatural beings are unseen by the larger population of Zion Pepe. However, at their pleasure and when necessary, they could be seen by prophets and any other member of the community whom they have decided to reveal themselves to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Angels as supernatural beings cannot be physically felt by the larger population of Zion Pepe inhabitants. However, at their pleasure and when necessary, they could allow their presence to be physically felt by prophets and any other member of the community whom they have decided to reveal themselves to

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community believes that non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world. Because they are conceived of as having superior knowledge to humans, they are seen as being able to intervene in several events happening in different locations at the same time. This attribute makes them, in the theology of Zion Pepe community to be seen as having superior knowledge of this world when compared to humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe, non-human supernatural beings are conceived of as having knowledge unrestricted to particular domain of human affairs. As supernatural beings, they are held as having unrestricted knowledge of the affairs of the

world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe, non-human supernatural beings are held as having knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region. Because they are above the natural, their capacity is seen as being above those of humans who are only restricted in their knowledge to places where they are physically present or where they are provided information by an eye witness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are held as having knowledge unrestricted within the sample region. In fact, their independent vast knowledge of events and incidences makes them better suited to supervise the operationalisation of the law of karma within and outside the sample region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are held as having knowledge unrestricted outside the sample region. In fact, their independent vast knowledge of events and incidences makes them better suited to supervise the operationalisation of the law of karma within and outside the sample region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, non-human supernatural beings can see all mortals everywhere normally visible (in public). Their capacity to see everyone in public is one of the reasons they are held as supernatural. Their capacity to see humans everywhere in public confers on them the very nature of supernatural

beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, non-human supernatural beings can see all mortals everywhere including in the dark and at home. Their capacity to see everyone everywhere is one of the reasons they are held as supernatural. This capacity confers on them the very nature of supernatural beings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind of human beings. This capacity includes their ability to see and recognise the hidden motives of all mortals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, non-human supernatural beings know the basic character (personal essence) of human beings. They are held as sharing in the divine nature of being all knowing as the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to all humans including what they will do in future. This falls within their nature of being all knowing of past, present and futurer events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Zion Pepe community holds non-human supernatural beings as having other knowledge on all topics relating to humans, plants, animals and other phenomena in this world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: As ministers in the theocratic government of the supreme high god, non-human supernatural beings share the attribute of deliberate causal efficacy of events with the high god in the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, these supernatural beings act as agents of the supreme high god when they reward the actions of human beings in the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: When the non-human supernatural beings punish the wrongdoings of human beings in the world, they do so as agents of the supreme being and not independently on their own authority.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe, supernatural beings as agents of the supreme being share in his powers as the custodian of direct causal efficacy in the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe theology, supernatural beings exhibit positive emotions like kindness, favour, being helpful, showing compassion among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, supernatural beings are held as scarcely exhibiting negative emotions. When they do, it is in the overall interest of the community of saints. They could burn with indignation in a bid to punish an individual for anti-social behaviours in a bid to stamp out evil from the land. They could as well be ruthless in executing vengeance on evil doers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: In Zion Pepe, the only form of hunger the supernatural beings could be said to exhibit is the hunger for repaying people for their past actions. The retribution could be a good one (positive reward) or a negative one (punishments for wrong doing).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Notes: Generally, the features which non-human supernatural beings in Zion Pepe possess are divided into two groups. They are generally good and protective but are also agents of justice. They equally punish every wrong doing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: There is no categorization of mixed human-divine beings in the theology of Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In the hierarchy of supernatural beings recognised by the Zion Pepe community, the supreme high god sits at the summit. He is supported by angels, the twelve (in some other cases twenty four) elders and other heavenly beings. All these heavenly (supernatural) beings are ministers in the supreme beings kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not view the supernatural beings they relate with as being organised by kinship based on family model.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: In the hierarchy of supernatural beings recognised by the Zion Pepe community, the supreme high god sits at the summit. He is supported by angels, the twelve (in some other cases twenty four) elders and other heavenly beings. All these heavenly (supernatural) beings are ministers in the supreme beings kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings recognised by Zion Pepe community are not restricted to specific domains in their capacity to intervene in the affairs of the people. However, some of them are specialists in certain tasks and duties. This does not mean that they cannot be saddled with other tasks outside of their areas of specialisation. Angel Michael for example is a warrior who fights all battles on behalf of the people. Angel Gabriel bears messages from the supreme being to the human community while also taking the requests of the human community up to the supreme being for his attention and intervention.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Notes: There are no other organization for pantheon in the categorization of supernatural beings in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, there is the belief that the eyes of the supernatural being are ever watching every action of all members of the human race. It does not matter whether the actions are done in secret or in the open. None of the actions of any mortal being goes without the supreme being's notice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the supernatural being monitors adherence to all prosocial norms and would reward obedience to them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the supernatural being cares about taboos.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Food:

– No

Notes: There are no forbidden foods in Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In former times, there was a space within the first church auditorium in Zion Pepe where the prophets (especially the monarch) seldom entered. Anytime they went into that arena to operate, spiritual interventions of significant proportions were sure to be recorded. It was regular for the monarch to halt the rampaging of witches and other sinister activities on such occasions. Another sacred space in Zion Pepe was the "So otito" spot. This was a space outside the church auditorium operated by the Cherubim Band. This band was responsible for the maintenance of law and order in the community. Part of their duties was to apprehend lawbreakers and conduct investigation into their deeds or activities. When matters got to a head and investigations got stalled due to the suppression of evidence, suspects were often taken to this spot and warned thoroughly to speak the truth. If they do, they would be spared of negative consequences. If they however refuse to speak the truth at this spot, they would be visited with a big calamity which shall expose their dishonesty to the whole community. These two spots are no longer in active use in the community today. A modern auditorium has been built although on the site of the old one, it has neutralised the spot within the old church. The "So otito" spot is still preserved but it is not in active use today. Plans are in place to revive the "So otito" spot.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are sacred objects used in worship in Zion Pepe community. Some of them include the bell used during prayers, the drum (called baalu in the local dialect), prayer garments, wooden crosses and swords used in spiritual exercises. However, of all the sacred objects in use in Zion Pepe community, the bible is the most significant.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Members of the Zion Pepe community belief that supernatural beings care about all aspects of their lives. They agree on the need to conduct themselves in manners that are acceptable to the supernatural beings to retain their goodwill and favour.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is a crime in Zion Pepe. There is no difference if the person murdered is a coreligionist or a non-member of the Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is a crime in Zion Pepe. There is no difference if the person murdered is a coreligionist or a non-member of the Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is a crime in Zion Pepe. There is no difference if the person who has been murdered is a coreligionist or a member of other polities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is one of the anti-social activities most frowned upon in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is a forbidden sexual act which is never tolerated in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Zion Pepe community frowns at bestiality, gay, queer, homosexual and lesbianism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that supernatural beings care about lying and dishonesty.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Because they hold that supernatural beings are always true to their promises, members of the Zion Pepe community also feel strongly about the need to keep their oaths both to humans and to supernatural beings. Members of the community have the conviction that for every promise/oath that proceeds from the mouth, humans would be brought to judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The virtue of hard work is highly encouraged in Zion Pepe community. Laziness is frowned among the population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe monarch and prophets devote a lot of time and energy fighting Sorcery and all those suspected to be involved in it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Fighting is considered an anti-social in Zion Pepe. It does not matter if the fight is a lethal or non-lethal fight.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that life in itself is full of risks. The community holds that reasonable risks are to be taken with a sense of duty and responsibility. In order to keep safe when taking reasonable risks, proper assessment of what needs to be done and the safest ways to conduct oneself are encouraged in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community cares about respect for elders and constituted authority. This is because they hold that supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, gossiping is considered an anti-social behaviour. They contend that their supernatural beings dislike the act because it breaks the bond of friendship and weakens the community spirit.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community upholds the sanctity of the ten commandments listed in the bible. One of the commandments states that believers should never covet their neighbour's property. They hold on to this and the other nine commandments religiously.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are meant to be conducted in prescribed manners following the laid down sequence. Zion Pepe community believes that supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that supernatural beings care about performance of rituals. The community holds religious meetings two times daily. They meet at 5:00 am for the sunrise congregational religious meeting and also at 5:00 pm for the evening congregational meeting. These hours of prayers/rituals are kept religiously.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Though Zion Pepe community holds that supernatural beings care about the conversion of non-religionists, they are very circumspect in their drive for proselyting. They seem to respect the choice of individuals to their religious views. Most of their programmes are held in their communities of faith while they keep their doors open to those who desire to know more about their faith. During such interactions, they allow their visitors make their choice on whether or not to join them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community beliefs that supernatural beings care about economic fairness. The community vehemently opposes the use of false scales and all forms of dishonesty in economic activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community promotes the need for personal hygiene on the basis of its contribution to personal and collective health and well being of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Zion Pepe community acknowledges the interest of the supernatural beings in all aspects of their personal and communal lives. They hold that the involvement of the supernatural beings in all areas of their lives ensures their all round success and wellbeing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Though the high god personally executes punishments on sinners and evildoers, he does not personally carry out punishments all the time. He uses other beings to execute punishments as he pleases.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, the belief is that when supernatural beings act as agents of enforcing punishments on wrongdoers, they do so on behalf of and in the interest of the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, the belief is that when impersonal cause-effect principles are activated as agents of enforcing punishments on wrongdoers, they operate in this capacity on behalf of and in the interest of the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, there are no restrictions to the array of entities or means by which the supreme being executes punishment on wrongdoers. Circumstances, common and uncommon incidents and even the elements of nature

as was the case with the biblical Joshua could be deployed to visit punishments on individuals and groups for disobeying divine instructions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments are meted out for wrongdoing as the supreme being pleases. One of the reasons for such punishment is to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The need to enforce group norms stands out as one of the reasons Zion Pepe community attributes to the necessity for punishments among their population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that some of their members could suffer punishments if they had exhibited acts of selfishness. The need to punish selfishness, according to them stems from necessity to discourage others from exhibiting such acts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not hold the view that punishments are meted out to people in a random manner among them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community believe that every punishment comes for a specific wrong done. They hold that evil will not fall on the lot of the righteous. This means that the righteous will never be wrongly punished.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community emphasises that supernatural punishments in the afterlife awaits everyone who during their earthly lives involves themselves evil acts and other acts of wrong doing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: The church does not hold the belief that punishment in the afterlife consists of

reincarnation as an inferior life form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: The church does not hold the belief that punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe believes that punishments in the afterlife consists of torment from poisonous insects and other venomous reptiles.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community teaches that supernatural punishments would be meted out to wrong doers and people who partake in anti social acts in this life

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, it is believed that people could suffer bad luck as a result their disobedience to divine instructions. According to them, this is possible because the divine being will no longer be interested in harkening to their request for his intervention as a result of their disobedience. His refusal to be involved in their lives therefore brings them bad luck.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Although the community is not in pursuit of a political empire or kingdom, Zion Pepe believes that the downturn in political successes of nations of the world is a direct result of the deviation of humanity from the path of truth and righteousness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community believes that life itself is a battle. So failure to succeed in any phase of life could be traced to some punishment for past wrongs. Except an individual is certain they have been upright in their ways, they may think their failure is a punishment for their disobedience.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe does not practise crop farming substantially. However, failure to return home with bountiful fish harvest from fishing expeditions in the sea, rivers or canals could be attributed to punishment for sin. This is not a general believe among the people as they are conscious of the effects of the tides and other natural phenomenon on the outcome of their fishing enterprise.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: When people experience disasters on journeys, some may ask if it is a result of their sins. However, this sentiment is not the norm among the people. The community recognises the role of mechanical faults, the contributions of the weather and the expertise of drivers to safe trips.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure. There is a subtle feeling in the community that humanity's original disobedience (the sins of the first man and woman; Adam and Eve) to the supernatural being is the main cause of every discomfort currently suffered by humans. These displeasures include visual, auditory impairment etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure. There is a subtle feeling in the community that humanity's original disobedience (the sins of the first man and woman; Adam and Eve) to the supernatural being is the main cause of every discomfort currently suffered by humans. Examples of extreme displeasures (punishments) which could be suffered in this life include severe sicknesses and death etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that sickness and death are two important examples of punishments which wrong doers could suffer in this life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that impaired reproduction is a significant punishment which wrong doers could suffer in this life

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the visitation of bad luck on descendants of wrong doers is a significant punishment their generation could suffer in this life

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the extent of the possibilities of punishments which wrong doers could suffer as a result of their actions is limitless.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the high god is at liberty to decide on the personality of individuals or groups to implement rewards to those found to be deserving of it. The high god himself could personally dish out the reward or may decide to commission another personality to carryout the act of reward sharing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community accepts that many supernatural beings play definite roles in dishing out rewards to humans for good deeds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that impersonal cause-effect principle plays a role in appropriating rewards to humans who have conducted themselves well.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that rewards which individuals receive for adhering to religious rituals could propel others to emulate such good examples so that proper conducts could be multiplied among the human race.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that rewards are dished out to deserving individuals so others could be encouraged to follow the path of acceptable conduct. This scenario definitely would serve to promote obedience to group norms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that rewards for good conduct has a way of encouraging others to conduct themselves properly. This promotes group values and banishes selfishness from the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community not not accept that rewards are given randomly. They hold that rewards are earned and not wished or given as bonuses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious

group:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community emphasises the existence of supernatural rewards in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe community teaches that sensory pleasures constitute reward for observance of group norms in the afterlife. Access to highly nourishing fruits, control over kingdoms and good music angelic orchestra are a few of the sensory pleasures the people hope to be treated to in the afterlife

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that a variety of sensory pleasures are components of the reward for observance of group norms in the afterlife. Some of the extreme pleasures humans will be treated to in the afterlife include exercising dominion over peoples and having all of one's desires met.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe, eternal happiness is a key component of the rewards people get for being obedient to divine instructions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not believe in reincarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not believe in reincarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: It is held in Zion Pepe that all things will be made new. This includes everything that has entered into the thought of the human race and those that have not been contemplated. Everything will assume new forms of splendour and grace. The experience is conceived of as incomparable to any that been contemplated by the human mind.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community emphasises the operationalisation of supernatural rewards in this life. This is why the community discourages her members from anti-social acts and all forms of wrongdoing which attract punishment. Instead, they encourage compliance with community norms because of the rewards that follow such acts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: When individuals adhere to group norms, Zion Pepe community believes they stand a good chance to experience good luck in their endeavours. This is because they would curry the favour of the supernatural being who bestows favours and good luck on those who act in accordance with the norms of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community teaches that the world would experience peace and progress politically when everyone follows the path of justice and fairness. They opine that when humans follow divine instructions on proper conduct, the polity would experience political stability and success.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Though Zion Pepe does not engage in military campaigns, the community holds that success in every aspect of their private and collective wellbeing depends on their adherence to divine instruction. They hold that good and evil forces contend fiercely daily for the souls of humans. This contention is a form of battle that needs to be fought and won. Individuals and groups exercise their freewill and decide either to follow the good and acceptable path or the evil and disapproved path. When they resist the evil suggestions, they are deemed victorious over the battles of life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: The Zion Pepe church holds that rewards in this life consists of peace or social stability. When the community or group of people follow divine instructions, they are more likely to experience peace and social stability.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that rewards in this life consists of success in their commercial and economic activities. However, since Zion Pepe is a community in the proximity of the Atlantic Ocean and a network of rivers and canals, they are not essentially an agrarian but a fishing community. So success in their fishing enterprise and the enjoyment of clement weather come as rewards to their good deeds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, success on journeys are considered as rewards in this

life. The community holds that those who conduct themselves in acceptable manners will suffer no evil but the evildoers will more often have rewards that are in tune with the paths they chose. So safe journeys come naturally to good people while misfortunes on journeys come more often to people who flout divine order. However, the constant battle between the good and evil forces makes the path of the good people to be clouded with traps intended to endanger their lives. If they are prayerful and careful, the traps will fail to catch them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the enjoyment of mild sensory pleasures as rewards that are available to good folks in this life. Generally speaking, the community holds that good things will happen to people who follow the right path always.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the enjoyment of extreme sensory pleasures as rewards that are available to good folks in this life. Generally speaking, the community holds that good things will happen to people who follow the right path always

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the enjoyment of enhanced health as rewards that are available to good folks in this life. Generally speaking, the community holds that good things will happen to people who follow the right path always

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the enjoyment of enhanced reproductive success as rewards that are available to good folks in this life. Generally speaking, the community holds that good things will happen to people who follow the right path always. They hold on to the provisions in the bible which says that "your children shall surround your table" and "none shall be barren among you".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that enjoyment of fortunes visited on descendants are rewards that are available to good folks in this life. Generally speaking, the community holds that good things will happen to people who follow the right path always. Again they hold on to the biblical saying ... "my children are for signs and wonders" and ... "the generation of the righteous is blessed".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community is clear about the fact that there is an endless possibilities of rewards for good people. No single list of rewards suggested at anytime can be exhaustive or capture all rewards that good folks can enjoy following their compliance with divine instructions. This serves to motivate people to keep exploring opportunities to act in manners prescribed by the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Messianic beliefs are present in Zion Pepe community. They believe Jesus Christ is the messiah who came to free them from the bondage and power of Satan, sin and death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the messiah's intervention in human affairs comes at strategic periods in human history. They believe that the messiah had made his first intervention in human affairs by coming to orchestrate a spiritual exercise that enables humans to have the capacity to reject the unwholesome suggestions of evil forces. The messiah will allow each individual exercise their freewill to either accept and follow the paths of his intervention or to reject it. There are consequences however for each path an individual chooses. At the second coming of the messiah, he shall reward the actions of each mortal. He shall reward those who follow his guidance and punish those who reject his advice. Regarding the messiah's

whereabout, the community holds that his is currently in heaven preparing the mansions those who obey him shall live in. He is also conceived of as pleading with the supreme high god on the behalf of the human race to see how more and more of the people shall be assisted to follow his path and escape the punishment that is to come.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: The messiah acknowledged by Zion Pepe community is believed to be alive and currently residing in heaven. Most people in the community cannot really tell how he looks but have an idea that he is a peace loving personality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the messiah shall come at the end of this age (world) to reward everyone according to the works they have done while in the flesh. While he is expected to give beautiful rewards the good folks, he shall punish the disobedient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the exact day of the return of the messiah is not known. Therefore, they encourage their members always to be ready for the messiah's return. This is because he shall reward each person going by their current actions at his return. The responsibility of perpetual proper conduct is on each individual so as not to miss the rewards from the messiah at his coming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The coming of the messiah according to Zion Pepe theology would be at an unspecified time in the near future. Although the community holds that the messiah would come soon, his anticipated coming has been long expected. In fact they hold the view of his coming in the near future which members of the early church held about 2000 years ago.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the coming of the messiah is imminent and in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: As earlier pointed out, the coming of the messiah in the Zion Pepe theology is two-fold. He has accomplished his initial coming and would yet come in the future to complete his assignment on earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Notes: The Zion Pepe community holds that there is only one messiah who has made his initial visit to the earth. According to them, he will come again to complete his mandate among the human race at a time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, the messiah's most important assignment is to come and save humanity from the grip of the evil one (Satan or the Devil). He is meant to redeem humanity back to the high god and repair the frosty relationship which was occasioned by the disobedience of humanity to the high god who loves them so dearly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: The community sees their messiah as a spiritual messiah. He is conceived of as one who saves humanity from the bondage of sin rather than the yoke of the oppression of a dominant political power. They hold that spiritual oppression is more significant when compared with physical/political subjugation. According to them,

political oppression ends on earth while spiritual oppression does not terminate in this present realm of existence. Satan has a desire to lead humans to Hades or hell where he will subject humans to eternal suffering, pain and anguish. To escape that unending plight awaiting those who surrender the sovereignty of their lives to Satan, the messiah came to perfect their bail and release form the impending eternal doom.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that the messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions and bridges the gap which disobedience has created between the supreme high god and humanity. They contend according to the bible that their messiah came to fulfil the law and the prophets. This means that he came to point the attention of the people to the laws and the path which the prophets have instructed them to follow.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The community holds that the messiah came to destroy the works of the devil and to restore humanity to the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community beliefs in eschatology. They emphasise the belief in the events that would lead to the end of the present world and the second coming of the messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the eschaton would happen in this lifetime. They belief that this world shall not pass away until the messiah returns.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: The community believes that the specific time of the end time events are not known and that they shall not be made known to humanity until they suddenly take place in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that eschaton shall take place at an unspecified time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not believe that eschaton will take place at an unspecified time in the distant future. They hold that though eschaton is a future event, it shall take place at an unspecified time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community is clear about the time of eschaton. It shall take place at an unspecified time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe does not hold the view that adherents have a mandate to perform specific tasks to bring about world's end. According to Zion Pepe theology, the world's end has been predicted or prophesied by prophets. Events would naturally lead to its occurrence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that divine judgement would take place in the future. This is held

as part of the end time events. It shall be executed by the supreme high god and the messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: As part of the end time events, Zion Pepe community holds that the messiah shall reign for a millennium on earth to show humanity what they missed when they gave the control of the world to Satan as a result of their disobedience of the supreme high god's instruction before he executes the final judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Notes: The community does not believe in the beginning of a new temporal cycle at the end of this current age (eschaton).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The new political system which Zion Pepe opines would be introduced at the end of this current world is the type which they currently practice; theocracy. They hold the conviction that this system of government was prescribed for them by the supreme high god and that it is the same that is in use in heaven. It shall remain in operation in the next age. An age which shall be under the control and supervision of the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that no new religious system shall be introduced in the world to come except the one which they currently practice..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that a specified number of individuals (144,000) who are otherwise convinced about a different modality for the coming of the messiah (the Judaic tradition) may survive the eschaton. This is however dependent on their perseverance during the tribulation and trial of their faith during the period when the anti-Christ shall hold sway on the earth (seven years of tribulation) immediately following the magical disappearance of the good people (rapture). This is found in the book of Revelations in the bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those religious in-group members who shall partake in rapture shall survive the eschaton. This is because they would have been removed from the earth which shall fall under the control of the anti-Christ for a period of seven years. Those who had been raptured shall return to the earth with the messiah for the millennial reign where the messiah shall demonstrate the bliss and perfect splendour which humanity missed when they chose to follow the suggestions of the devil rather than the injunctions of the supreme being which is more beneficial to them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Only those religious in-group members who shall partake in rapture shall survive the eschaton. This is because they would have been removed from the earth which shall fall under the control of the anti-Christ for a period of seven years. This group shall strictly consist of those who were exceptionally obedient to divine instructions. It is therefore no good to just belong to the community and refuse to follow the divine mandate of obedience to the prescribed way instituted by the messiah. This is because those who refuse to adhere to the community's accepted norms based on the messiah's prescription shall also partake of the punishment which awaits all folks who live in disobedience to divine mandate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that their members who refuse to adhere to the messiah's injunctions would miss the rapture and remain on earth during the seven years cruel reign of the anti-Christ. The possibility of surviving this eschaton of this period is very slim if not impossible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The community does not hold the belief that everyone in the world would survive the eschaton. They believe that it would only be easy for those who submit to the conditions set by the anti-Christ would survive the eschaton. However, obedience to the conditions set by the anti-Christ automatically excludes them from enjoying eternal bliss. This is because they would have pledged their souls to the devil who controls the anti-Christ and their policies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community prescribes general social norms for her members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: This is not exactly so. The moral injunctions in the community crystallise into the convention the community follows. However, when it comes to a recent practice regarding their acquiescence of pre-marital sexual relations, the community has rather been permissive of the practice among their population of young people. This is in spite of the fact that their conventions forbids it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community promotes Honesty, trustworthiness and integrity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Courage (in battle):**

– Yes

Notes: The community encourages courage when faced with any daunting task or situation in life. They do not engage in military campaigns as part of their religious obligations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Courage (generic):**

– Yes

Notes: The community encourages courage when faced with any daunting task or situation in life. They do not engage in military campaigns as part of their religious obligations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:**

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community prescribes compassion, empathy, kindness and benevolence as virtues to be upheld and followed by their members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:**

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches the imperative of mercy, forgiveness and tolerance among her members. This is because they hold that unless we all forgive those who offend us, the supreme high god would not also forgive our many wrongdoings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Generosity / charity:**

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community advocates strongly the need for generosity and charity among her members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Selflessness and selfless giving are important attributes Zion Pepe community preaches among her members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community is particular about the need for her members to uphold righteousness and moral uprightness in their conduct daily

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: The community advocates for ritual purity, ritual adherence and abstention from sources of impurity. Members are encouraged to follow these spiritual obligations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: Respect and courtesy are two important virtues which Zion Pepe community teaches her members to uphold and practice always.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches the primacy of familial obedience and filial piety. Members of the community are encouraged to obey the supreme high god and give maximum respect to their parents as long as the wishes of their parents do not conflict with that of the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe teaches fidelity and loyalty as important virtues to be embraced by every member of their community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Cooperation, togetherness and unity are germane attributes the community teaches her members towards their spiritual wholeness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community encourages her members to be independent, creative and exercise their freedom with decorum in such a manner that they would not break the divine instructions put in place by the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: The church keeps their member in remembrance of the need for moderation and frugality in their conducts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community hold forbearance, fortitude and patience as vital character traits their members need to uphold at all times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Diligence, self-discipline and excellence form part of the core virtues Zion Pepe community teaches her members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: In Zion Pepe community, assertiveness, decisiveness, confidence and initiative are built into the character of their members. This enables them to live and maximise their potentials.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community admonishes her members to engage their challenges with all their physical strength in a bid to overcome them and make progress in their life's journey.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Power, status and nobility are not engaged in the negative sense in Zion Pepe. The church teaches that power, status and nobility are to be used constructively and to the benefit of the majority of the people. The community believes that power should be used to rescue the weak while status should never be a tool for exploitation. They also hold that nobility should be not confer undue advantage on people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community teaches her members to imbibe humility and modesty in their daily conduct.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches contentment, serenity and equanimity among her members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe admonishes joyfulness, enthusiasm and cheerfulness among her members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches optimism and hope among her members in order to achieve their dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe theocratic community teaches her members that thankfulness and gratitude are important attributes which they must embrace to get more favours from the supernatural beings and other humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community teaches that reverence, awe and wonders must be ascribed to the divine being to continue to attract his blessings in their daily lives

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community holds that faith, belief, trust and devotion are expected of members to continue to attract the supreme being's favour and approval.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community are admonished to obtain and exhibit the virtues of wisdom and understanding. They hold on to the biblical injunction which says "wisdom is the principal thing. In all your getting, get wisdom and obtain understanding"

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community are admonished to be full of discernment and strive to display intelligence in their engagements.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community are taught to cultivate or groom their beauty and attractiveness. However, the beauty of their character should be a priority to them above physical beauty.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community prioritises cleanliness (physical) and orderliness and so ensures their community is always kept clean. They hold that cleanliness is an important part of their spiritual service.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Holiness, punctuality to appointments, fairness and justice are a few of the other important virtues advocated by Zion Pepe religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No member of the Zion Pepe community is expected to practice celibacy. In fact, just like in many Yoruba communities within the sample region, polygamy is practiced in Zion Pepe by a large proportion of the population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: There are no constraints on sexual activities between married partners in Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is not practiced by humans in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: There are times when members can elect to undertake fasting and prayer in Zion Pepe community. As it is generally accepted in Zion Pepe, when fasting is added to prayers and supplication, it brings more profound results. This forms the basis for personal and occasional community fasting in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: There are no taboos on foods in Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Permanent scarring or painful body alterations are not conditions for membership in Zion Pepe theocratic community..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Membership of Zion Pepe community does not require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is done in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is required in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: There is no basis for self sacrifice and suicide as conditions for church membership in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Sacrifice of property or valuable items is not a requirement for membership of Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: As with most organizations, membership of Zion Pepe requires sacrifice of time in the form of attendance at meetings or services and regular prayers etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Physical risk taking is not a condition for membership of Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Membership of Zion Pepe community requires acceptance and practice of ethical precepts which the community considers important to its existence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community are not expected to marginalise others who are not members of their community neither do they accept acts of marginalisation from others on the basis of their identification with the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Notes: Generally, the community teaches that her members are expected to pray to the supreme being at least every morning when they wake up and at night when they are about retiring to bed. Families in Zion Pepe community are also encouraged to pray together daily.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

Notes: On average, about a hundred people attend the twice daily church meetings in Zion Pepe community. The community church is open for prayer at 5:00 am and at 5:00 pm. At these meetings, at least a hundred people gather to pray. The number is often above this figure in many instances. However, during their anniversaries, conventions and other important ceremonies, thousands of worshippers gather to observe religious activities in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 12

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: No orthodoxy checks are institutionalised during religious meetings or ritual observances in Zion Pepe

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: No orthopraxy checks are institutionalised during religious meetings or ritual observances in Zion Pepe

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Notes: Synchronic practices are not institutionalised in religious meetings or ritual observances in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are not used in any religious activity in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Notes: Tattoos/scarification are not practiced as religious activities Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Circumcision:**

– Yes

Notes: Male infants in Zion Pepe community are circumcised just as it is done in most parts of Yorubaland.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Food taboos:**

– No

Notes: There are no food taboos in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Hair:**

– No

Notes: There are no strict hair styles, colouring or treatment done by members of the Zion Pepe community. Generally, male members keep their hair trimmed while female members as it is prevalent in other Yoruba communities groom their hair and keep them in good condition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Dress:**

– Yes

Notes: Prayer garments are in use in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Ornaments:**

– No

Notes: There are no ornaments stipulated for use in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ **Archaic ritual language:**

– Yes

Notes: Some of the religious specialists, especially prophets use Glossolalia in prayers and ritual

performances in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Several other extra-ritual markers exist in Zion Pepe community. Some of them include music, dancing etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: The use of fictive kinship terminology is universal in Zion Pepe community. People in the religious community refer to themselves as brothers and sisters even though they are not related by blood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The use of fictive kinship terminology is both universal and widespread in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is employed and very common in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Cherubim and Seraphim Society sees itself as a big band of saints. In the understanding of Zion Pepe community, the Cherubim is a band of heavenly beings actively engaged in fighting spiritual warfare while the seraphim is the entire collection of all Christians. So when the church refers to itself as the Cherubim and Seraphim Society, they speak of themselves as the body of Christians constituted into a band in pursuit of a unified goal of spiritual dimension.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe community cares about the physical wellbeing of her members. During the period when the community was being built, many of her their members were financially unstable. The community therefore provided for the needs of the people including their nutritional needs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community directly handles its programme of famine relief to the group's adherents.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: During the formative period of the community, it provided some form of poverty relief to its members just to get them started. Some of the relief provided included fishing nets and other gears needed to allow them launch into the rivers and the Atlantic Ocean for their fishing enterprises.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community directly handles its programme of poverty relief to the group's adherents.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The community does not directly provide institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm. It is the responsibility of their family to meet their needs. The community however comes to the rescue when the family is unable to play the role effectively.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No internal or external group or individuals provides institutional care for the elderly or infirm in Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Zion Pepe provided scholarships to children within the community in their formative years. The community built both primary and secondary schools where their children received standard education while growing up

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: All members of the community had access to the education provided in their schools.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: The community handled all aspects of the education it provided for her members. It did not outsource the structure or any aspect of her educational services.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is no strict bureaucracy in Zion Pepe community. However, there is a council of elders which assists the monarch in running the community. This council is made up of wise men and religious functionaries (prophets) within the community. They do not constitute themselves into a bureaucracy but just function to keep the community running in the overall interest of everyone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Notes: The group's adherents do not directly interact with any institutional bureaucracy as individuals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not provide public food storage for her members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution outside of the religious group provides public food storage to Zion Pepe members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The community does not provide water management in any form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution outside of the religious group provides water management to the people of Zion Pepe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: In the past Zion Pepe ran a boat transport scheme which conveyed people and goods and also supported service delivery across several hundreds of kilometres on the Nigeria's coastline.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution outside of the group has been responsible for providing transport infrastructure for Zion Pepe members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not levy taxes or tithes. Only full members of the community (those who have completed the community's theology training) are required to make charitable contribution less than 25 British pence monthly towards keeping the community running.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian government levies taxes on the adult population of Zion Pepe just as they do with other citizens of the country across the country's territory.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The Cherubim band carries out the functions of the Police in Zion Pepe

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In recent times, the Nigeria Police Force has began to extend their security coverage to Zion Pepe. This is because the Cherubim band's capacity to provide adequate security coverage for the community has declined.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not provide institutionalised judges. The community submits itself to the judges of the Nigerian court system.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with the Nigerian judicial system. They accept the Nigerian governance system and are guided by the sovereignty of the Nigerian State.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not arrogate any powers to itself to execute members accused of breaking laws and conventions of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Members who commit infractions considered abhorrent to the community's core beliefs are in some cases expelled or sent on exile. Infractions which could attract expulsion includes adultery.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: In the past, corporal punishments were handed down to members on the basis of the severity of their offense. Members could be asked to weed some communal areas, fetch sand to fill portions of the waterlogged areas of the community etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Ostracism was practiced in Zion Pepe in the past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community does not seize properties of their erring members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian government through its judicial process enforces institutionalised punishments on members Zion Pepe community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian State still retains execution as a capital punishment within its territory.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: The Nigerian Government does not send her citizens on exile outside of the national borders. In very rare cases, the government had sent some deposed traditional rulers on exile from their kingdoms. However, the Nigerian Judicial system has overruled the government on such decisions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: The Nigerian government does not deploy corporal punishment while punishing her citizens for any act against the state.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: The Nigerian government does not ostracise her citizens

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Except when the property is secured through criminal acts, the government does not seize properties of her citizens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe does not have a formal legal code. However, there are no ambiguity regarding the governance structure in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian government legislates upon and enforces the laws on all peoples and spaces within its territories. Zion Pepe community being an integral part of Nigeria is governed by the formal legal codes instituted in Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe does not possess an institutionalised military. The Cherubim band in the community exists to maintain internal security and law and order within the religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community are free to join the Nigerian military and serve to protect the external integrity of their nation, Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Zion Pepe community are protected by and subject to the Nigerian Military comprising of the Navy, Air Force and Army.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess its own distinct written language. The Yoruba language which the Ilaje people speak is in use in Zion Pepe, an integral part of Ilajeland.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba language (a non-religion-specific written language) is available to the group's adherents customarily in their part of Yorubaland in Nigeria

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba language (a non-religion-specific written language) is available to the group's adherents customarily in their part of Yorubaland in Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Zion Pepe community uses the Gregorian calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government of Nigeria where Zion Pepe is located provides guidelines for political, religious, economic, educational activities and other important events which Zion Pepe recognises and follows as it affects them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: When Zion Pepe was newly established some of her members found it difficult to meet their personal needs. The community therefore established a communal farm where members worked in groups to cultivate crops. When harvesting was done, the farm output was shared among the members for sustenance. Other small scale farming practices also aided the supply chain of food commodities within Zion Pepe. Since the community is located within the precinct of the Atlantic Ocean, some members went regularly to the sea to fish and were quite generous with their catch such that they made some of it available for members who had not the opportunity gather fish from the water bodies that surrounded the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution other than the religious group provides food to the group's adherents.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

